

PHONEME RECOGNITION WITH BINAURAL COCHLEAR MODELS AND THE STEREAUSIS REPRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes phoneme recognition experiments which use biologically motivated dual channel collection and processing of speech corrupted by noise. The signals are processed by head-related transfer functions to produce right and left side signals which are then input to cochlear models. The cochlear outputs are combined using the stereausis algorithm to produce feature vectors which are classified by a self-organizing feature map. Binaural collection and processing is shown to improve recognition rates over a single channel system for certain conditions and broad class speech sounds.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that most current speech recognition systems use a single channel and are adversely affected by noise. It is also well known that the ability of humans to binaurally collect and combine signals from two ears improves the recognition of speech in complex environments. Recent efforts have used single channel models of the human auditory system to provide features useful for speech recognition [1, 2]. This paper describes phoneme recognition experiments using biologically motivated dual channel collection and processing of speech corrupted by noise. The goal is to improve recognition of degraded speech over the monaural case by modeling certain known aspects of the binaural auditory system. Experimental results show the binaural system improves performance under certain conditions for some broad class sounds.

The next section presents background information about binaural collection and using stereausis for binaural combining. In the following section, experiments are described and results presented. The final section discusses these results and suggests further research.

2. BINAURAL HEARING

2.1. Binaural Collection

Binaural collection begins with the two external ears separated by a head. The sound wave interacts with the head, external ears, and ear canals on its path to the eardrums. This arrangement provides time of arrival, intensity, and spectral shape differences between the signals for sources not directly in front of or behind the listener. The ear on the side opposite the source receives a delayed, lowpass filtered and attenuated version of the signal at the other ear. The delay is due to the path length difference between ears

while the lowpass filtering and attenuation are due to losses as sounds travel around the head.

The above aspects of binaural collection have been simulated by models of the head-related transfer function (HRTF). A method for combining the outputs of two cochlear models is now described.

2.2. Binaural Combining

Stereausis is a process for combining binaurally collected sounds. Shamma and colleagues have described this process in a biologically plausible manner [3]. Mead and associates have recently made an analog VLSI processor which computes the stereausis representation and suggest its application to speech recognition [4].

The stereausis representation is the set of cross-correlations between all output channels of the left and right cochlear models. The correlation measure used here is $c_{i,j}(k) = [x_i(k) + y_j(k)]^2$ as described by Shamma and others in [3] where $x_i(k)$ and $y_j(k)$ are the i^{th} and j^{th} left and right cochlear channel outputs at sample index k .

The cochlear model used in this work has a filter bank representation of the basilar membrane, followed by stages to simulate fluid-cilia coupling and inner hair cell transduction within the cochlea [5]. The output of the cochlea is a set of averaged firing probabilities for 66 channels. Detailed information regarding the human cochlea may be found in Pickles [6].

Stereausis responses may be intuitively judged by forming an image. In this paper, images are produced by linearly averaging instantaneous stereausis responses for 12.5 ms as in [3]. Darkness is proportional to the amplitude of the response. Figure 1(a) is the image for identical 1100 Hz sinusoids in both channels, and 1(b) results from sinusoids with a phase difference of 120° (or $303 \mu\text{s}$). Images will be symmetric for identical signals in both channels as in 1(a); energy is shifted off the main diagonal ($i = j$) for signals that are delayed between the two channels, as in 1(b).

Consider the situation of identical speech sounds in each ear and noise that is delayed in one ear with respect to the other. The main diagonal then provides a set of features where the speech energy is concentrated and the noise energy reduced. This offers the promise of providing a robust representation for the condition which corresponds to the case of a speaker directly in front of or behind the listener with noise energy incident at some nonzero azimuth angle.

Stereausis images for a vowel and fricative are shown in Figure 1(c) and 1(d). Note the two patterns characteristic

of sinusoids in 1(c) due to the formants of the vowel. Also notice that in 1(d), the high frequency energy characteristic of a fricative. The differences among the broad class sounds also provide some promise for success using stereausis as a tool for phoneme recognition.

3. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION AND RESULTS

3.1. Speech Database

The sampled speech data are a subset of the DARPA TIMIT Acoustic-Phonetic Continuous Speech Corpus. The data were recorded in a quiet environment and sampled at 16 kHz with 16 bits per sample. The subset consists of seven male and three female speakers from four different dialect regions of the United States. Each speaker read ten sentences, two of which were common to all speakers.

3.2. Processing Stages

Figure 2 shows the four major processing stages of the experiments. Speech and noise directions are synthesized separately and then added to produce the right and left channels for subsequent processing by the pair of cochlear models. Two methods are used to synthesize binaural signals. In the first method, left and right cochlear inputs are related by a time delay. The second method uses the empirically measured HRTFs of Wightman and Kistler [7]. Here, signals are processed by two digital filters to generate inputs to the two cochlear models. These HRTF filters provide appropriate time delays, intensity differences, and spectral shaping as a function of angle. Conditions simulated are that of a fixed power noise source at the indicated angle interfering with on-axis speech. Details of signal to noise ratio estimates are given in section 3.4.

The second processing stage is a pair of cochlear models which compute the average firing probability of inner hair cells covering the frequency range of 550 to 8000 Hz [3, 5]. The third stage computes the stereausis response along the main diagonal every sample interval. The outputs are averaged over a 20 ms window to produce one feature vector. The averaging window is then advanced by 5 ms and a new feature vector calculated. The fourth stage performs speaker independent phoneme recognition using an 8x8 self-organizing feature map with a dot product distortion measure.

3.3. Training and Testing

Speaker independent results are calculated using the "hold one out" method on a per speaker basis. The resultant classifier is trained with the speech from nine speakers. Then, speech from the held out speaker is used to test this classifier. This procedure is repeated nine more times. Thus, values presented in the results are averages over ten classifiers. This method provides reasonable estimates should the system be used for a speaker not in the database.

Each classifier is a self-organizing feature map. After training, learning is disabled and all the training data are presented again to the feature map. The node with the maximum response to each feature vector is assigned the phoneme label associated with that feature vector. The phoneme label with the largest number of responses at each

category	Condition (S/N = 20 dB)			
	monaural	$\Delta = 0$	$\Delta = 5$	$\Delta = 10$
correct	31.5	32.3	34.3*	32.5
deletion	12.9	7.9*	7.4*	8.0
insertion	5.3	4.9	4.9	4.8
substitution	50.3	55.0*	53.4*	54.7*
fricatives	25.2	41.5*	40.8*	37.0
glides	16.7	20.0	22.8	27.6
nasals	31.1	27.4	26.7	30.4
silence	78.3	79.7	79.6	80.2
stops	23.3	21.7	27.3	22.7
vowels	81.4	84.9	84.7	82.2
broad class	59.1	64.7*	65.2*	64.3*

Table 1: Results from experiments using a delay to simulate noise locations. Statistically significant differences with respect to the monaural condition are marked with a *.

node is assigned as the label for that node. During testing, the phoneme label of the node with the maximum response is assigned to the input feature vector. Thirty-eight phoneme classes plus silence are identified from roughly 6500 feature vectors during each testing session.

3.4. Conditions

The conditions considered are listed in Tables 1 and 2. In Table 1, "monaural" is used to describe the case of speech plus noise input to a single cochlear model. The next three conditions use interchannel delay to synthesize azimuth location of the noise source. Equivalent angular locations corresponding to the delays are calculated using a spherical head approximation. The 0, 5, and 10 sample delays correspond to angles of 0°, 36°, and 84.9°. The speech signal is input directly to both cochlear models without an interchannel delay to simulate an on-axis speaker.

In Table 2, the column labeled "one ear" refers to the situation where the speech plus noise signal is processed by only one of the two HRTF filters for 0° azimuth. The last four columns are for 0° speech and noise at the indicated angles processed with both HRTF filters.

Different signal to noise ratios result between the conditions given in the two tables due to HRTF filtering. The noise source is assumed to be of fixed power with selectable azimuth. Prior to processing by the HRTFs, the average signal to noise ratio is 20 dB. Therefore, when azimuth location is synthesized by interchannel delay only, the average signal to noise ratio is 20 dB. However, when HRTFs are used to synthesize azimuth location, the signal to noise ratios in each channel become a function of the selected angle to the noise source. The signal to noise ratios at the inputs to the right and left side cochlear models for the range of experimental conditions are shown in Table 3.

3.5. Results

Phoneme recognition results are shown in Tables 1 and 2. All results are given as percentages. One-sided *t*-tests are used to determine statistical significance of the mean difference between processing methods. The reference condition for both tables is the monaural column in Table 1. Results from ten speakers provide nine degrees of freedom for each

category	Condition (for S/N, see Table 3)				
	one ear	0°	30°	60°	90°
correct	31.2	32.6	33.2*	32.2	33.0*
deletion	12.8	11.0	9.6*	9.9*	10.5*
insertion	4.2*	3.2*	3.7*	4.5*	4.0*
substitution	51.7	52.6*	53.5*	53.4*	52.5*
fricatives	44.3*	47.9*	47.6*	45.4*	52.7*
glides	19.3	15.5	11.0	11.7	15.4
nasals	8.9*	10.0*	10.9*	4.5*	11.6*
silence	82.4*	84.2*	84.4*	81.1*	83.4*
stops	5.3*	4.8*	5.1*	3.8*	4.0*
vowels	76.5	82.6	84.0	84.7	81.6
broad class	59.0	62.0*	62.2*	60.8*	61.9*

Table 2: Results from experiments using the HRTF of Wightman and Kistler to synthesize speech and noise locations. Statistically significant differences with respect to the monaural condition of Table 1 are marked with a *.

condition tested. Statistical significance with at least 95% confidence is denoted in the tables by a *.

Table 1 presents results for binaural synthesis using only interchannel time delays. HRTFs are used to synthesize binaural signals for the results in Table 2. The categories presented are now described.

Phonemes properly recognized are labeled "correct". Phonemes misclassified as silence are labeled "deletion" while "insertion" refers to silence misclassified as a phoneme. Phonemes incorrectly identified as other phonemes are labeled "substitution". Broad class performance is tabulated for fricatives, glides, nasals, silence, stops, and vowels. The label "broad class" corresponds to phonemes assigned to their proper broad class categories.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Interpretation of Results

Binaural processing was expected to improve recognition performance for situations where the speech and noise have different angular positions. In this discussion, conclusions are made only for statistically significant results.

The percent of phonemes correctly identified increases for $\Delta = 5$, and at 30° and 90°. This supports the idea that the stereausis main diagonal provides some robustness in noise. Note that this improvement is not due to HRTF spectral shaping only since the one ear case is not different (in a statistically significant sense) than the monaural case.

The deletion rate drops as a function of noise angle for four of the five non-zero azimuths. Also notice that the insertion rate drops for all cases where HRTF filter(s) are used. This suggests that binaural processing assists in the discrimination of silence versus phonemes. The substitution rate increases in all binaural cases. Further investigation into the actual phonemes substituted is necessary to make further comment on this effect.

Broad class performance is mixed. There are no differences in recognition rates for glides and vowels between the monaural and any other condition. However, fricative recognition increases by at least 15.6% for six of the seven binaural conditions. Some of this improvement may be due

to HRTF filtering, but some benefit is due to binaural processing as seen by the improvements in all binaural cases over the single channel cases.

Nasal and stop performance is much worse for all HRTF filtered cases while there is no difference in performance for the delay only binaural synthesis. One possible explanation is the HRTF spectral shaping reducing gain over frequencies where these phonemes concentrate their energy. Silence recognition rates increase for all HRTF conditions but no change results with delay only synthesis. This suggests that the benefit is due primarily to HRTF filtering, not binaural processing.

4.2. Further Research

The mixed results above indicate that some combination of monaural and binaural processing would improve the recognition rates for these conditions. This arrangement has been proposed in models of binaural hearing [8]. Future work includes classifying outputs from each cochlea in addition to the outputs from the stereausis main diagonal. Decisions of three classifiers could then be fused in an attempt to improve performance.

All results here are due to feature vectors from only the main diagonal of the stereausis response. Use of entire images will be necessary to apply this method for arbitrary speaker and noise azimuth locations.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. R. Anderson, "Speaker independent phoneme recognition with an auditory model and a neural network: A comparison with traditional techniques," in *Proceedings of the 1991 International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, (New York), pp. 149-152, IEEE Press, 1991.
- [2] M. J. Hunt and C. Lefebvre, "Speaker dependent and independent speech recognition experiments with an auditory model," in *Proceedings of the 1988 International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, (New York), pp. 215-218, IEEE Press, 1988.
- [3] S. A. Shamma, N. Shen, and P. Gopalaswamy, "Stereausis: Binaural processing without neural delays," *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.*, vol. 86, pp. 989 - 1006, Sep 1989.
- [4] C. A. Mead, X. Arreguit, and J. Lazzaro, "Analog VLSI model of binaural hearing," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 230-236, 1991.
- [5] S. A. Shamma, R. S. Chadwick, W. J. Wilbur, K. A. Morrish, and J. Rinzel, "A biophysical model of cochlear processing: Intensity dependence of pure tone responses," *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.*, vol. 80, pp. 133 - 145, Jul 1986.
- [6] J. O. Pickles, *An Introduction to the Physiology of Hearing*. San Diego, CA: Academic Press, second ed., 1988.
- [7] F. L. Wightman and D. J. Kistler, "Headphone simulation of free-field listening. I: Stimulus synthesis," *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.*, vol. 85, no. 2, pp. 858-867, 1989.
- [8] J. V. Tobias, *Foundations of Modern Auditory Theory*. New York, NY: Academic Press, 1972.

Figure 1: Stereausis images for (a) centered 1100 Hz sinusoid; (b) same as in (a) but with a 120° phase shift between channels; (c) steady state vowel /iy/ as in “she”; (d) steady state fricative /sh/ as in “she”.

Figure 2: Diagram of processing stages. For the conditions reported in Table 1, the HRTF is a time delay only. The results of Table 2 use the HRTFs of Wightman and Kistler.

condition	SNR (dB)	
	left	right
monaural	20.0	—
one ear	13.7	—
$\Delta = 0, 5, 10$	20.0	20.0
0°	13.7	13.3
30°	18.1	10.6
60°	22.2	9.7
90°	19.6	12.0

Table 3: Signal to noise ratios at the inputs to the cochlear models for the range of experimental conditions.